

Figure 1. The first 19 cities wired by *Socrate*.

The red markers indicate those cities in which the cabling was almost completed whereas other key-cities such as Milan (in black) rejected *Socrate* supporting other wiring companies.

Source: Author's elaboration of collected data

Figure 2. Percentage of individuals using the internet in G7 countries.

In 1995 only U.S. had more than 15% users accessing the Internet

Source: Author's elaboration of ITU data

Figure 3. A screenshot of the navigable map of the civic network platform IPerBOLE in 1997.

Each building corresponded to a specific service, the interface was aimed at overcoming linguistic diversities so as to include tourists and migrant citizens.

Source: Maurizio Matteuzzi's personal archive

The Italian network hopes

Rise and fall of the *Socrate* and *Iperbole* projects in the mid-1990s

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Abstract

The paper retraces the histories of two Italian networking projects of the mid-1990s: the national infrastructural plan named *Socrate*, launched by the monopolist *Telecom Italia* in 1994 and the civic network *Iperbole*, launched by the municipality of Bologna in 1995. Relying upon a corpus of primary sources and in-depth interviews with key-informants, the paper stresses the complex relationship between infrastructures, networks and media imaginaries in Italy at a time when the large-scale diffusion of the Internet and the World Wide Web were still *in fieri*. The same years of the WWW's first diffusion were in fact a period of negotiation at local, national, and international level between various actors and different ways of envisioning the upcoming digital age. The paper shows how the history of *Socrate* challenges the idea of the centrality of the Web and the Internet in company discourses of the mid-1990s juxtaposing a different narrative and an imaginary of networking infrastructures linked to broadcasting media. Conversely the case of *Iperbole* is a particular example of public service use of the Internet on the wave of a political and cultural tradition that looked at media as strategic tools, rather than theoretical models, for democratisation.

Keywords: *Socrate*; *Iperbole*; network histories; internet imaginary; 1990s; *Telecom Italia*

Introduction: searching for the Italian network histories

In his critical stance against the hagiographic history of the internet, the historian Andrew Russell makes a plea for a new concept aimed at decentring the term *Internet* from historical accounts of networking (Russell 2017). Relying on this proposition, this paper considers the shift from *Internet history* to *the histories of networking* suggested by Russell as a theoretical key for another analytical transition from the analysis of the *internet imaginary* (Flichy 2007) to the investigation of the plural *network imaginaries*.

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By doing so, this approach takes also into account the historical role of other networks and *media imaginaries* (Natale & Balbi, 2014) for the construction of technical and social digital infrastructures like the two Italian projects analysed in this paper.

In a seminal work for the analysis of the Internet imaginary, Thomas Streeter has shown how the internet of the 1990s was not just a technology but rather “the enactment of a hope. The changes of 1993-1995 were very much *anticipatory*, changes based on what people *imagined could happen*, not what had already happened (Streeter, 2011: 135 emphases added). In Italy, as in several other countries, the imaginative power described by Streeter did not apply only to the Internet, but to networks at large interpreted as the core-structures of upcoming the “digital age”; rather than being confined to the realm of the Internet, the *network* concept is in fact the cornerstone of modern technologies and ideologies starting at least from the 18th century (Musso 2016).

Situated in the crucial phase of the 1990s, the two case studies analysed in this paper - the *Socrate* project led by the monopolist *Telecom Italia* and the civic network *Iperbole* led by the municipality of Bologna - represent two co-existing and opposite poles in the Italian histories and imaginaries of networks. As this work aims to show, *Socrate* was a huge project for a national infrastructure that threw the cable network ‘from above’ adopting, rather than a distributed model, a broadcasting-oriented vision; on the other hand, the civic network *Iperbole* represents a clear attempt to embed the Internet and the distributed model of communication within a longstanding project of political democratisation. From a network histories perspective, the two projects were thus only partially influenced by the mainstream narratives of the Internet of the 1990s.

Notably, if compared to mainstream narratives of Internet history, the projects led by the monopolist telecommunication company and by the Bolognese municipality

1 followed two different trajectories in terms of networking structures, contents and
2 imagined users. In sum, the *network imaginaries* of the 1990s in the Italian context
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4 diverged from the dominant narrative of internet history that looks at the 1990s as the
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6 age in which a fixed and unique imaginary spread worldwide. Indeed, the *Italian way to*
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8 *the digital age* was shaped by technological visions of the future which were in line
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10 with the country's cultural and economic traditions as much as in its internal
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12 geographical and political fragmentation.
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16 The analysis of the two cases relies on primary sources from national, companies
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18 and digital archives, and on a series of in-depth interviews with key informants. The
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20 work is structured in 4 parts: The first paragraph resumes the networks landscape in
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22 Italy at the beginning of the 1990s with a focus on the legacy of former projects realized
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24 in the 1970s and the 1980s. The second and third paragraphs retrace the
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26 conceptualisation and the development of the two projects *Socrate* and *Iperbole* in the
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28 mid-1990s. In the fourth paragraph, the two case studies are compared in order to shade
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30 a light on the different imaginaries that shaped their development over time. This
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32 analytical part also stresses the divergence between the case studies in terms of
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34 networking models and the relevance of imaginaries for the eventual failure of both
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36 projects. The papers ends up suggesting to intertwine the Italian case with other network
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38 histories in order to retrace points of contact, similarities and divergences among
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40 infrastructural and networking projects in European and Western countries.
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50 **The Italian networks landscape in the early 1990s**

51 The Italian networks landscape in the early 1990s resulted from a long series of
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53 successful and failed projects both at scientific and industrial level. Notably, starting
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55 from the 1970s, Italy was actively involved in the construction of digital networking
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57 infrastructures at industrial level, with a special expertise in connecting components
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1 such as fibre optical cables. For example, in 1977, four Italian companies - *CSELT*, *SIP*,
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4 switchboards by optical cables. The wire took place in Turin, the mother city of the
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6 monopolist telecommunication company *SIP* (then renamed *Telecom Italia* and now,
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8 almost two decades after the privatization, *TIM*). A few years later, between 1984 and
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10 1991, , the *State Company for Telephone Services* (*ASST*), *SIP* (now on *Telecom Italia*)
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12 and *Pirelli* built an articulated long-distance fiber optic infrastructure with two
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14 complementary projects: the first one, the *Progetto 80*, laid around 6.500 Km of optic
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16 cables all along the Italian highways; the second one, the project *Festoni*, realized for
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18 the Football World Championship *Italia 90*, wired the Italian West coast by means of
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20 subsea optic fiber cables from the South to the North (Bordoni 2002: 39-40). By the
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22 early 1990s, the Italian long distance infrastructure was complete whereas short distance
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24 infrastructures were lacking both in the rural and urban areas of the country.
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27 Furthermore, beside these partial progresses at infrastructural level, during the 1980s the
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29 future application of the digitalized infrastructures was still uncertain. This theoretical
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31 gap between the technical and the techno-logical progress was well represented by the
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33 struggle between two Italian players around the meaning of a key term: *packet*
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35 *switching*. Notably, starting from the early 1980s, the *State Company for Telephone*
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37 *Services* (which was responsible for the *Telex* services) and *Telecom Italia* (which
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39 managed telephone services) struggled for the management of digital packet switching
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41 networks claiming their respective right to handle and control the new data transmission
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43 systems. The *ASST* claimed that packet switching systems were the natural evolution of
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45 the *Telex* system, whereas *Telecom Italia* claimed that packet switching data were the
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47 evolution of the telephonic system. In 1992, after many years of internal dispute, the
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49 telecommunication ministry gave charge of the network infrastructures to *Telecom*
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1 Italia. Eventually, this decision was taken by the Ministry because of the lack of human
2 and economic governmental resources which were essential to handle a growing sector
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4 needing more and more experts and permanent employees. As result, in the early 1990s,
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6 Telecom Italia had almost complete control of the Italian telecommunication system,
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8 data networks included, and it took the main responsibility for the national transition to
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10 digitalization. It was in this moment that the executive managers of the company started
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12 to think about a short distance infrastructure able to connect the long-distance optic
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14 fiber network with households so as to spread the digitalization process all over the
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16 country and build up an advanced, competitive digital infrastructure.
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20 However, in the early 1990s the main contents and services that Telecom Italia would
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22 provide to users through the new digitalized networks were not clear at all. In particular,
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24 systems like the World Wide Web would definitely spread only a decade later and the
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26 Italian media system was going through a radical change due to the success of the
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28 mobile phone industry and the success of private broadcasting companies such as Silvio
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30 Berlusconi's *Mediaset*. At academic level, the first connection to the Internet in 1986
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32 and the growth of scientific networks were highly underestimated at industrial but also
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34 at public level. In the mid-1990s in the Italian context was thus influenced by a
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36 heterogeneous media landscape in which uncertainties and multiple visions of the
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38 technological future drove the creation of different networking projects at macro and
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40 micro level; these projects would eventually conflict and fail because of a scarce degree
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42 of cohesion at political and cultural level between the key actors of the Italian transition
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44 to digitalization.
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54 **The *Socrate* project: a national infrastructure for the information age**

55 With an expected investment of more than 12 thousand billion Italian Lira
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57 (around 6 billion Euros, the half actually spent) the *Socrate* project was one of the
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1 highest investments in the Italian history of telecommunications. Notably, *Socrate* (an
2 acronym that means *optical-coaxial development of the telecommunications access*
3 *network*) was created in 1994 by the monopolist *Telecom Italia* to face two main
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highest investments in the Italian history of telecommunications. Notably, *Socrate* (an acronym that means *optical-coaxial development of the telecommunications access network*) was created in 1994 by the monopolist *Telecom Italia* to face two main upcoming challenges. First, the liberalization of the telecommunication market in Europe in 1998 would open a cruel competition among telecom companies. To protect its leading position in the market, *Telecom Italia* planned to create a new national infrastructure connecting the main Italian cities (Fig. 1) so as to keep control over the network and to “force” new providers to use its new infrastructure. The second reason behind the launch of the project was to sustain the overgrowing amount of data needed to create the new services expected from the upcoming information age. After three years of huge investments and bargaining, the project failed mainly for economic reasons.

At the beginning, Ernesto Pascale, the CEO of the holding controlling *Telecom Italia*, promoted the project in public debates, often through strong statements like the following one:

Cabling is the technological evolution of telecommunications; we would do it for the telephone even without the interactive multimedia market. We are anticipating investments that will stimulate the supply of services over time. [...] I am confident in the multimedia market, I am sure that we are at the beginning of an era that will change our way of working. I feel *in my flesh* that this is going to happen; this means higher investments, new subjects and higher occupation.

(Pascale, audio recording, 1995b, emphases added)

In this excerpt Pascale emphasised the high expectations towards the digital age, showing his deep faith in a technological change that would take place all over the world. According to Pascale *cabling* was seen as a priority for the future of Italy, a country that would soon face a new, disrupting scenario. However, if the disruptive

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change of the digital age was taken for granted, the actual shape of such change was very uncertain especially in terms of services and contents.

From a technical point of view, *Socrate* contained a peculiar feature: the final path of the network, the so-called *last-mile* (the path connecting the network cabinets to buildings), was not made of fibre optic cables but it was wired through coaxial cables, thus it imitated the broadcasting networks' infrastructures of countries such as the U.S. and U.K. Considering the lower costs and the consolidated tradition of this specific infrastructure, Telecom chose to use the so-called *hybrid fibre-coaxial* (HFC) network; this structure allowed a large receiving bandwidth at the time (with a downstream power of around 1.5 Mb) and a low upstream bandwidth (around 64 Kb). In this way, any form of connection was particularly apt at receiving a huge amount of data rather than sending information up throughout the network. In brief, *Socrate* allowed a partial and asymmetric use of the fibre optic capability because of its slow-upstream speed due to the coaxial element.

Relying on this technical aspect, and in order to get an immediate economic return, *Telecom Italia* decided to fill up the infrastructure with a specific kind of contents; video on demand (VOD). More specifically, a new company founded by *STET*, named *Stream*, was given responsibility for the VOD services, with a budget of around 2 billion Lira (Adnkronos 1993). Trying to lure Italian customers to the new technology, *Stream*'s business strategy was based on one of the most loved programs of Italian people: football matches. *Telecom Italia*' strategy for the new market was thus based on an old, well-known technology (HFCs were already employed for cable TV in other countries) and on a safe and certain set of contents. According to the monopolist VOD services would have been essential to recover a strategic investment that would allow the company to control the national broadband infrastructure for data transmission

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for a long time. Nevertheless, according to the former co-director of STET Umberto de Julio, the decision to bet on football matches broadcasting proved to be a double-edged choice:

Television meant two things to politics, politicians and public opinion: football and news. Nobody cared about other things, but if you touched these things, it was a serious problem, it meant touching the distribution of contents among TV networks. (Umberto De Julio, personal communication, September 15, 2016)

Indeed, the decision to bet on broadcasting services was one of the key causes of the failure of *Socrate*. According to Telecom Italia managers, broadcasting companies such as Silvio Berlusconi's *Mediaset* and the public broadcaster *RAI*, did not accept to switch from the traditional ether-based transmissions to digital TV, thus making *Stream* the unique actor in the cable TV sector. At the time Berlusconi, who had just won the election in 1994, was taking advantage of his political power to protect his broadcasting company (the only one allowed to operate at a national level), and thus maintaining the status quo of the Italian duopoly *RAI/Mediaset*. The *Mammì law* of 1990 had legitimised *de facto* Berlusconi's monopoly on commercial TV and even the left-wing government led by Romano Prodi in 1996 opted for a non-intervention policy in the sensitive broadcasting sector (Balbi & Prario, 2010; D'Arma, 2015). In sum, the balance between the two (one public and one commercial) broadcasters entailed a resistance both at political and economic level towards the potential integration of a new actor in the market. Indeed, after the missed agreement with *Rai* and *Fininvest* and the failure of *Stream*, *Telecom Italia* decided to not cross the borders of the broadcasting sector for several years (Ortoleva 2005).

Furthermore, even if *Stream* was successfully tested (for free) on 1000 customers in Milan, eventually Italians were not attracted by the new, unknown, VOD platform

1 offered by *Stream*, preferring their habitual, reassuring, analogic TV schedule.

2 Moreover, pay-tv services like football matches and movies were already provided by
3 the Berlusconi's and the film producer Vittorio Cecchi Gori's *Tele+*. Launched in 1990
4 *Tele+* was already available under subscription and it was clearly the main, and only,
5 competitor of *Stream* in the pay TV sector. In 1996 *Tele+* switched from analogue to
6 satellite transmission adding more channels to its show schedule. From its side, the
7 *Stream* service required the acquisition of a new decoder (which was different from
8 *Tele+* so customers should have 2 decoders to access both services), the annoying
9 installation of the coaxial cable in each apartment, and the familiarization with the new
10 streaming platform. *Telecom Italian* immediately understood that, in order to compete
11 with *Tele+* and to not lose ground with competitors, *Stream* had to transmit also on
12 satellite. Eventually, this decision also compromised the original purpose of the
13 company to transmit via cable so as to feed the *Socrate* infrastructure.

14 From another perspective, *Telecom Italia* had to face an unexpected technological
15 innovation; the rapid development of the ADSL in the mid-1990s suddenly downsized
16 the utility of the HFC network since copper cables became re-usable for data
17 transmission, also providing users with a larger bandwidth than *Socrate*. Besides these
18 technical and commercial issues, probably the main cause of the failure was the political
19 resistance of municipal politicians and the difficult process of cabling in the some key
20 Italian cities such as Bologna and Milan. As the former *IEEE* president and *Telecom*
21 *Italia* manager Maurizio Décina argues:

22 To send cables to houses, we had to dig, and *Socrate* was mainly doing this:
23 digging. Municipalities gave us permits but they asked expensive street renovation
24 works in return that caused huge expenses.

25 (Maurizio Décina, personal communication, November 9, 2015)

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The struggle with municipalities slew down the digging process increasing the human and economic resources needed for the realization of the infrastructure.

In wider terms, there was neither a cooperative attitude among institutional players nor a responsive marketplace for the project. A few years later, in its historical account, Telecom itself would admit that in that period:

There was everything but probably what we missed was the market [...]. The technology and the market did not meet each other, because digital television increases thanks to satellites and DVDs, which are available almost in every single block, at vending machines or in specialized stores. [...] Furthermore, to make matters worse, in late 1990s, beside this growing amount of contents and supply points, the Internet came to mix everything up.

(Telecom Italia Lab, 2004: 149)

Above all, the failure in the media market was due to the weak attraction of Italian customers and users to broadband-based services. In this regard, the Telecom research engineer Ivano Camerano claims:

When looking back at the mid-1990s we have understood that it was too early. First, because technology was not enough mature to provide an infrastructure that could really be useful, beyond any project or dream, to provide a value in terms of broadband connections. Above all, however, the main problem was that we, as Italians and Europeans, were not ready for broadband services at all. Someone claimed, ‘We will get thousands of information and VOD services’, but in the end the bottom line was that we were not used to it, we lacked of mentality of this approach. In the U.S., it was completely different.

(Ivano Camerano, personal communication, October 15, 2015)

The expression “lack of mentality” summarizes a crucial aspect of the network imaginary characteristic of *Telecom Italia* and, we can argue, of the Italian context at large during the mid-1990s; the expected use, the future, and thus the *meaning* and *functions* of both computer and digital networks were not clearly prefigured by media

1 and business actors as well as by the different strata of the population. The uncertainty
2 of the *digital age* was in this sense self-evident, as it is a matter of fact that the Internet
3 and the Web, in the mid-1990s, were not seen by *Telecom Italia* as the future of
4 communication but only as one of the possible novelties in the chaotic global media
5 landscape. In the meantime, the Internet and the Web were spreading mainly in the U.S.
6 and, more slowly, in other European countries. The Italian delay in terms of
7 technological development and strategic visions would influence the infrastructural *gap*
8 between Italy and the rest of Europe in the following decades. As Maurizio Décina
9 argues referring to the current situation in Italy “We are last because we started last.”
10 (Maurizio Dècina, personal communication, November 9, 2015)
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The civic network *Iperbole*: a local network imaginary

27 While *Telecom Italia* was investing a lot of human and economic resources on
28 *Socrate*, some Italian academic and political players were starting to pay attention to the
29 growth and the potential of the Internet, relying on a different vision of the future of
30 networking systems. A few months before the public launch of *Socrate*, one of the most
31 interesting experimentations of Internet use in Italy was taking place in Bologna. In
32 1993, the council member Stefano Bonaga and the philosopher of language Maurizio
33 Matteuzzi created, with the support of the mayor Walter Vitali, the civic network
34 *Iperbole*, an acronym which stands for *Internet “For” Bologna and Emilia Romagna*.
35 Notably, *Iperbole* was the second civic network in Europe and the first in the world
36 providing free Internet access to citizenship. Before *Iperbole*, the first European project
37 was the well-known *Digital Stade* of Amsterdam, founded in 1992 (Downey &
38 McGuigan, 1999, pp. 91-92). It is important to note that *Iperbole* was conceived before
39 the release of the World Wide Web into public domain, thus it was not directly
40 influenced by the birth of what is globally perceived as *the* revolutionary system of the
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1990s, or, as Bonaga used to call it, the “*full Internet*” (Stefano Bonaga, personal communication, October 21, 2015). Thanks to an intense cooperation between public and academic institutions (e.g., the main access node of the network was provided by the academic supercomputing center *CINECA* of Bologna), *Iperbole* gained an outstanding success and it received the attention of international organizations and institutions such as the *European Union* and the *G7* meeting of 1995 (McDonough, 1995). By 1996 more than the 15% of the citizens of Bologna had a personal Internet access and an email account, a very high percentage if compared for instance with the Internet access in *G7* countries at the time (Fig. 2). Thanks to a free platform accessible through a personal username and password (Fig. 3), citizens could access the following services from a set of computers placed in municipal buildings (and later on also from personal computers downloading a free software on CD-ROM):

- Full Internet access
- Personal email account and communication with municipal services (e.g., asking information about public services, municipal laws, police stations etc.).
- Discussion groups created by the municipality
- Newsgroups on Usenet
- Direct and remote training to the “absolute beginners”

Before the launch of the platform, the municipality offered free training to staff, even if according to Damian Tambini (1998: 86-87), digital literacy was not as fast as the local government imagined. Actually, the early user base of *Iperbole* was mostly made of young, male students or managers, who were already literate citizens. Even if discussion groups were usually set up by the municipality, citizens could also create their own groups. As the history of the Arpanet mailing lists teaches us, leisure interests can prevail over serious topics, as some titles of the citizens’ discussion groups aptly show:

1 *Bologna by night, cooking, swap shop, sport and jokes exchange.* However, other
2 groups such as *Politics, work, Metropolis, university and health* were listed among the
3 most accessed on the network (Tambini 1998: 96-97). Moreover, in 1997 200 local
4 organizations promoted their Web pages and groups on the platform, involving citizens
5 in online polls and collective discussion with the municipality. Unfortunately, the the
6 municipality was not able to manage the growing amount of messages downsizing the
7 activist spirit of the network.
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12 Notwithstanding the difficulties met by the project, the ideas lying behind its foundation
13 were very innovative. Notably, the first proposal of *Iperbole* is extremely relevant for
14 the analysis of the imaginary characterising the project and an important community of
15 the Italian territory. *Iperbole*, in fact, was interpreted more than as a simple public
16 service; it was part of a wider political vision aimed at using technological tools such as
17 the Internet for the active participation of citizenship. As the two founders Stefano
18 Bonaga and Sergio Matteuzzi wrote in the first proposal of the project in 1993:
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35 It must be assumed as a starting point that technology now makes possible a wide
36 range of direct and real democracy applications: direct as it is done in person
37 without the mediation of delegates; real, as it is interactive and bidirectional, not
38 one-to-one. The project does not only find in the Municipality of Bologna a subject
39 interested in technology but also a natural context for its actual realization: *the city*
40 *is, at this stage, the strategic subject indispensable in fostering the take-off of*
41 *computer democracy.* In this political context, characterized by the increasing
42 incidence of television power, with the filtering and simplification of languages on
43 how to conform to democracy, it is of paramount importance that local authorities
44 are aware of the importance of disseminating information, thus of the widest scope
45 of public debate to become pioneers in democratic bottom-up experiments.
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53 (Comune di Bologna 1993: 6 emphases added)
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57 In Italy, the idea of a city that plays the role of an intermediary, we could say a *medium*,
58 through which electronic democracy could take place, was extremely innovative and
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1 powerful at the time. This vision would enhance social and political agency contributing
2 to the imaginary construction of a *networked citizenship*. In a successive paragraph
3
4 titled *The democratic city as bottom-up innovation*, the idea of a horizontal citizenship
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6 able to share, construct and even decide on public issues is stressed more in depth:
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10 The innovation of this project is therefore linked primarily to the active, conscious,
11 and strategic role of the public administration in stimulating computer democracy
12 and administrative transparency and in orientating *the future use of cable*
13 *communications towards low cost collective participation rather than towards a*
14 *further articulation of the entertainment and information-entertainment business.*

15 Another innovative aspect, of great political value, is that of users' digital literacy.
16 [...] Being in a democratic local network means not only providing machines and
17 software, but above all to literate, educate, write, respond, read, spread information
18 properly, and search for it effectively. To create a user who is actively conversing
19 in a civil way, who knows how to argue with and search for the right interlocutors.
20 In sum, it is all about creating *a form of interactive communication opposed to the*
21 *television paradigm* in which the citizen is conceived as a passive spectator of
22 phenomena on which he is not stimulated to participate. Only a local democratic
23 institution such as an elected administration and the citizens themselves may have
24 the political will and the concrete capacity to break the laces of an obsolete model
25 and developing a real electronic democracy.
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27 (Comune di Bologna 1993: 7 emphases added)
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40 From a theoretical - and clearly ideological – perspective, *Iperbole* was in strong
41 contrast with the *Socrate* project. As a consequence, Bonaga and Matteuzzi pursued a
42 battle against the centralisation of information (Musiani & Schafer, 2011) entailed in
43 services inspired by broadcasting television, which were interpreted by the two founders
44 as negative environments “in which the citizen is conceived as a passive spectator”.
45 Hence, the core-idea of *Iperbole* was to use the Internet as an instrument to realize a
46 political transition from representative to direct democracy; from delegation to first
47 person action; from verticality to horizontality; from entertainment media to
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1 participative networks. It is important to note that, although the Internet was the chosen
2 tool for the actual realization of this process, technology was not seen as the main cause
3 of social change; in particular, the Internet was not the reference model for social
4 change as it was, for example, to the imaginary conveyed by the Web's inventor Tim
5 Berners-Lee (*Author removed*). Networks such as the Internet and the Web were rather
6 seen as pragmatic instruments for the realisation of a political and cultural change that,
7 especially within the Bolognese activist community, had been at the center of political
8 and public debates since a long time.

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Indeed, throughout history and starting at least two decades before the birth of *Iperbole*, Bologna, which is also called *La Rossa - The Red One* for its historical leftist orientation, had played a key role in the construction of alternative forms of political participation; in several occasions, local political movements tried to integrate mass and telecommunication media such as radio, press and telephony into political activism. An interesting example of this *praxis* is the countercultural experimentations of the 1970s, when the pirate and free left-wing radio movements were created in Italy. In Bologna, in 1976-1977, *Radio Alice*, a pirate radio based on communitarian political participation, gained a great success also arousing the interest of influential intellectuals and opinion leaders like Félix Guattari. A key-figure of the leftist Italian intellectual landscape, the Italian philosopher Franco Berardi, took an active part in this *Alice* project. When recalling *Radio Alice*, Berardi stresses the fact that the rhizomatic network, a theoretical form conceptualised by Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari (1977) close to the distributed network model, was already central in the imaginary of Bolognese activists and intellectuals:

In 1977, Deleuze and Guattari published this booklet, *Rhizome*, it was to us like Mao's red book was before. They said that the history of Western capitalism is

1 based on the tree and the hierarchical order but we now discover a model of social
2 life based on the rhizome, a totally a-centric system in which each point is the
3 centre of the world. The concept of rhizome appeared to us as the utopian model of
4 the society we had to build and it was what we were actually doing with the free
5 radios! We said "we are on the right track!" [...] I came from the experience of the
6 free radio where we had already experienced this issue in Italy, especially with
7 Radio Alice; we always insisted that the radio is a centralizing medium but, with
8 the phone, it can become an a-centric medium. Nowadays, I have understood that
9 we misinterpreted what we saw as the sun of the future that was instead the new
10 stage of the history of capitalism.

11 (Franco Berardi, personal communication, October 19, 2015)

12 According to Berardi, the combination of radio and telephony had already been
13 seen as a possible solution for the realization of the distributed model of
14 communication particular to both the Internet and the Web imaginaries. But the
15 main difference of projects such as *Iperbole* and *Radio Alice* from the idealised
16 Internet of the 1990s lies in the role, the agency, of technology in social and
17 political processes; whereas the Internet imaginary has historically paid more
18 attention to the *effects* of technological structures and infrastructures on the
19 organization of societies, the imaginary of these alternative projects is deeply
20 rooted in political and cultural programs that have always conceived technology
21 more as an *instrument* than as a *cause* of change. This difference in terms social
22 responsibility was at the hearth of the struggle between *Iperbole* and *Socrate*..

23 ***Socrate* and *Iperbole* as conflicting network imaginaries**

24 *Socrate* and *Iperbole* represent two contrasting visions of the meaning and the
25 role of networking infrastructures in the Italian society of the 1990s. This conceptual
26 difference reflects also the different networks of relations and, no less important, the

1 forms and scale of power that struggled in Italy during a key transitional stage for the
2 digital market.
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4 Given the profound divergence in views, it is not surprising that the Bolognese
5 administration and *Telecom Italia* managers had a tough conflict during this period:
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7 from its side, the municipality wanted to supervise and control the construction of any
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9 new infrastructure also opening the market to different competitors, on the other side
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11 *Telecom* needed to cable a strategic hub of the Italian network to maintain its monopoly.
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14 Eventually, *Socrate* and the first version of *Iperbole* met each other for a very short
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16 time; the cables of *Telecom* did not cross the doors of Bologna until 1997, thus a few
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18 months before the failure of the project and after Bonaga left *Iperbole* for political
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20 divergences with the major and the local government. According to Bonaga, *Socrate*
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22 represented an opposite and negative vision of the information society; it was a
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24 centralized network oriented towards a vertical control of the infrastructure which
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26 should have been, instead, a common, equally distributed good:
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35 I stopped *Socrate* in Bologna. I stopped it for years because it was a folly. It was
36 very important for them to link Bologna because of its geographic position. [...]
37 Nobody remembers it but it was a crazy battle. Pascale came by private jet and
38 stepped into my small office to ask to cable Bologna. He came every three days!
39 We did not give him the authorization to dig. We proposed an alternative project,
40 *Optubi*, which was the opposite of *Socrate*. The idea was to use sewers and
41 electricity pipes to cut the costs, but it was above all for economic democracy
42 because they could put more cables, competitors as well, and the municipality
43 could control the territory. Moreover, the municipality would earn a lot because it
44 provided more than half of the excavation value. Instead, today three private
45 companies control the territory for the ultra-broadband and the municipality plays
46 the sole role of "facilitator". It has no political and social control of any kind. I am
47 very fond of this. *Iperbole* is an acronym which stands for *Internet "For" Bologna*
48 *and Emilia Romagna*. *Socrate*, on the opposite, reiterated a crime that has been
49 going on for decades in the Italian economy. We have lagged behind for decades
50 because of that project, just like the highways in Southern Italy: empty highways.
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(Stefano Bonaga, personal communication, October 21, 2015, emphases added)

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3 This quote explicates the main territory of conflict between *Telecom Italia* and *Iperbole*:
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5 on the one hand the centralised control of infrastructure at company level, on the other a
6
7 public and democratic distribution of a common good. It is to contrast ideologically the
8
9 idea of a centralised structure that Bonaga subverts the positive quality traditionally
10
11 attributed to the famous *information superhighway* metaphor, a concept largely adopted
12
13 in the corporate communication of *Telecom Italia* and even in academic and technical
14
15 reports on the wave of the discourses of the U.S. vice-president Al Gore (e.g.
16
17 Chirichigno 1995; Richeri 1995). Similarly, even though under a less ideological and
18
19 more pragmatic framework, the *Iperbole* co-founder Maurizio Matteuzzi criticised the
20
21 agenda and the management of *Telecom Italia* in that period:
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28 We have never towed the Telecom line. They launched the *Socrate* plan; they did a
29
30 lot of stuff. [...] Cabling was too important at the time for them; the mistake from
31
32 my point of view was from a network policy perspective. First they should think
33
34 about services, only after about cabling.

35 (Maurizio Matteuzzi, personal communication, November 2, 2015)
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38 This idea of *Socrate* wiring “empty cables”, is also shared by the media scholar
39
40 Giuseppe Richeri who worked as consultant for *Telecom Italia* in the 1990s:
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44 The *Socrate* project was overly technological deterministic. In those years
45
46 convergence was an ambiguous concept. *Socrate* was mainly based on technology,
47
48 with the idea that everything can be transmitted on the same infrastructure. There
49
50 was a technical convergence, but few paid attention to the convergence of content
51
52 and services. The main concern was on the container. There was little reasoning
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54 about the contents.

55 (Giuseppe Richeri, personal communication, October 2, 2015)
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However, the deterministic idea based on the motto “If you build it they will come” (Kozak 2015), thus on a *natural* and self-fulfilling development of contents and services as direct consequences of the presence of infrastructures, was not a distinctive trait of *Telecom Italia*. Notably, the Italian company shared this deterministic vision with other national and international players who were promoting the construction of national infrastructures without providing a reliable guideline in terms of services and contents. As the media historian Stephanie Ricker Schulte has shown, the mental representations of networks were not univocal at the time, “but instead overlapped, contradicted, competed, and dovetailed with one another, sometimes simultaneously.” (Schulte, 2013, p. 1) During the 1990s, the European Union was pushing national states to build and connect digital infrastructures able to bear the liberalization of the market. European institutions had a sort of *urgency for infrastructures* to survive the competition and the growing dominance of the U.S. in the new digital marketplace, even if the nucleus of this market was not clear at all. On the very same wavelength, Italian politicians tended to stress this urgency for connectivity, often adopting some suggestive metaphors and analogies with the national industrial history:

The multimedia revolution will not happen spontaneously. There is a need for short-term availability of broadband telecommunications infrastructures, which means to get a simultaneous broadcasting of voice, data and video services, all spread over the territory and accessible at low budget. This infrastructure (which can perform the same functions of the railway network during the first industrial revolution and which will represent the distinctive feature of developed countries) is essentially the wiring of the territory with fiber optic cables.
(Bosco 1995: 5)

1 Drawing upon the railway metaphor (rather than on the more common highway one) the
2 Italian government highlighted the importance of fibre optic infrastructures for the
3 development of the ambiguous multimedia market.
4

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6
7 As I highlighted before, the CEO of *STET* Ernesto Pascale was certain of the relevance
8 of cabling interpreted as a key-step for the future of societies. Notably yet, Pascale also
9 blindly trusted that interactive television, rather than the Internet, would be the chosen
10 medium for the actual transition to the digital age:
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18 A new revolution is about to start. It will be the interactive multimedia television in
19 1997; that will be the real revolution. Today we are in a preliminary phase. [...]

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21 There will be a chain of exchange, the so-called information society, especially in
22 entertainment. A new TV will be added to the general TV with which it will
23 compete. Tele-market and distribution chains will change. This also applies to
24 banks, tour operators and education. An additional, supplementary, and in part
25 substitute world is coming up, and it offers tremendous opportunities.
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29 (Pascale, audio recording, 1995a)
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33 Within Telecom Italia, whereas interactive television was perceived as a *natural*
34 evolution of traditional broadcasting, the Internet, and the Web especially, were
35 seen as mysterious objects. Umberto De Julio described his first experience with
36 navigation as follows:
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44 The Internet was like it did not exist. I remember when Maurizio Dècina came in
45 my office and said: 'I want to show you the internet'. Trecordi arranged an internet
46 connection and I remember I felt a mixture of anguish and something else. It was
47 like I was abandoned in the sea. It was like seeing a new dimension was coming
48 up, a dimension that was absolutely unknown at the time. So we knew how to play
49 in the market but there was no such thing as an 'internet offer' strategy [...]. We
50 were trying to understand, I became consultant for Vint Cerf. I used to visit him
51 every 4-5 months in the U.S., and then he came to Italy to teach internal seminars
52 because we wanted to get into this world. However, we had just launched *Socrate*
53 and we were in the middle of the outstanding success of the mobile... We had two
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1 great paths ahead: the first was the broadband network, and the other was the
2 mobile phone.

3 (Umberto De Julio, personal communication, September 15, 2016)
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6 This excerpt contains two relevant features of the media and network imaginaries of
7 *Telecom Italia* during the 1990s. On the one hand, De Julio perfectly conveys the
8 feeling of the sublime (Mosco 2004), going even behind its digital declination. Indeed,
9 it is difficult to find a better description of the sublime in its original romantic meaning
10 than “a mixture of anguish and something else. It was like I was abandoned in the sea”.
11 On the other hand, De Julio subtly discloses the fact that the Internet was largely
12 overlooked by *Telecom Italia*, primarily because of the main focus on broadband
13 infrastructures and mobile telephony, but also because of the high risk that an additional
14 investment on an unknown and new technology would have entailed for the future of
15 the company. Finally, there is a key difference between the market strategies adopted by
16 Italian and U.S. companies respectively: whilst in Italy technological innovations and
17 market strategies were in charge of a traditional and vertical structure represented by the
18 telecommunication monopoly, in the U.S. the growth of Internet-based companies and
19 services such as Netscape, Google and Yahoo relied on start-ups investing on young
20 project managers who bet on a new system (the Web) seizing the potential of a
21 decentralised model. Making a slightly forced analogy, in the area of networking
22 projects Italy did not bet on the Silicon Valley, it bet on the AT&T.
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47 On another wavelength, the parallel history of *Iperbole* shows the co-existence of
48 contrasting network imaginaries in Italy during the 1990s. The Bolognese civic network
49 was considered a pioneering experiment of Internet use and it also relied on a local
50 political tradition that was mixing technological innovations and social action since a
51 long time. Furthermore, from an historical perspective, the role of the municipality of
52 Bologna as an *intermediator* between citizenship and new digital environments is
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1 slightly distant from the *cyberspace* myth promoted by U.S. idealists such as John Perry
2 Barlow (1996) and Nicholas Negroponte (1995). The Internet was rather seen by the
3
4 Bolognese actors as an environment in which political participation, real life, and active
5
6 citizenship could meet and discuss horizontally: more than a territory to be discovered,
7
8 as in the U.S. imaginary outlined by Patrice Flichy (2007), *Iperbole* looked at the
9
10 Internet as a tool for the reinforcement of the public sphere, as a democratic space in
11
12 which civic education and public dialogue among citizens could take place.
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14 Unfortunately, after a series of struggles with *Telecom Italia*'s leaders and after the
15
16 decision of the mayor of Bologna to eventually accept the *Socrate*'s infrastructure,
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18 Stefano Bonaga resigned; in the years to come *Iperbole* lost its interactive dimension
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20 becoming a classical, mainly unidirectional, institutional platform. On the long run, the
21
22 dramatic failure of *Socrate* and the normalisation of *Iperbole* dragged the two project
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24 into oblivion.
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31 32 33 **Conclusions**

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35 During an interview, with a wry smile on his face, a former *Telecom Italia*
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37 manager noted that there is only one point in common between the Greek philosopher
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39 Socrates and the *Socrate* project: "at the end, they both shared the same destiny". From
40
41 its part *Iperbole*, notwithstanding its initial success, was rapidly forgotten after the
42
43 resignation of the founder Stefano Bonaga. As several other cases in network histories,
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45 the two projects represent two different, alternative paths, to the construction and
46
47 conceptualisation of networks during the 1990s at national and local levels.
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52 Notably, both projects were quite far from the narratives characterising the
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54 Internet imaginary of the 1990s. Rather than opening up an undiscovered territory
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56 (Flichy 2007), a cyberspace, to be explored or an alternative environment to be lived
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58 anonymously (Turkle, 1995), *Socrate* and *Iperbole* were constructed relying on the
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1 experiences of the past, thus on technological and political traditions, drawing also on
2 an *Italian style* (Fari, Balbi & Richeri, 2014) which characterised the long path to the
3 digitization of the country. As shown before, the digital sublime (Mosco, 2004), the
4 total faith in the power of technology to drive change, permeated the ideas of the future
5 of *Telecom Italia* as well as other European countries. Though, such faith was
6 influenced by what the sociologist Alberto Abruzzese defines a “national history of the
7 collective imaginary.” (Abruzzese, 2001, p. 56) In this regard, there are some critical
8 points of divergence between the Italian networking projects and the Internet imaginary
9 of the 1990s. For instance, rather than following the famous path towards de-
10 centralisation and distribution, *Socrate* was conceived following a principle of
11 dissemination (Peters, 1999) according to which the centralisation of infrastructure and
12 the vertical transmission of contents were essential to provide the best public service
13 and to concurrently maintain control within the new, competitive digital market.
14 Conversely, the civic network *Iperbole* embedded the horizontal principle of the
15 Internet within an institutional project that relied on the militant tradition of its political
16 communities.

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39 Generally speaking, if compared to the dominant narrative of Internet history
40 (*Author removed*), these two cases seem to be outdated and not relevant for what
41 concern the contemporary Italian and global contexts. Nevertheless, if looked
42 retrospectively, *Socrate* and *Iperbole* were both somehow anticipatory. Nowadays, a
43 VOD service like *Netflix* boasts a relevant share of Internet traffic in Western countries
44 (Hughes, 2016); if we consider platforms like *Youtube* a contemporary form of VOD,
45 the percentage is even higher. Hence, the broadcasting-oriented vision of *Socrate* was
46 not so far from the present use of broadband infrastructures; a-symmetric and vertical
47 communication is nowadays preponderant in the digital marketplace.
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